

NEGATIVE EFFECT OF HIGH CURRENTS IN ADDITIVE MANUFACTURED PARTS OF AL-5356 ALLOY

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ABSTRACT: This paper investigates the impact of 3D printing parameters using the cold metal transfer (CMT) technique on the morphological, mechanical, and tribological properties of walls and massive parts made from aluminum alloy. The essential parameter studied is current intensity and its behavior on manufactured parts. Using the technique mentioned above that are walls and massive parts with different filling strategies, using grid and zigzag patterns and at different current intensities. The main goal of the article is to know the drawbacks of using high currents and to find out the welding parameters suitable for having parts with low defects and improved properties from morphological, mechanical and tribological properties point of view of CMTed parts of Al-5356 alloy. It has been observed from the results thus obtained that the high current intensity causes rapid solidification, resulting a high porosity and low hardness values. Furthermore, the results show that there is an evident relationship between hardness, coefficient of friction and wear test. Some interesting results are presented in this paper.

KEYWORDS: Cold metal transfer, Aluminum alloy, current intensity, porosity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Additive manufacturing, in particular the (CMT) technique, is offering a novel perspective to manufacturers especially in the automobile industry [1]. The latter requires a lightweight and high strength product in order benefit a reduced fuel consumption. The use of Aluminium alloy is thus necessary. AlMg5Cr (A) (Al-5356) is one of the most wide and increasingly used aluminum alloys due to their light weight and high corrosion resistance [2,3]. However, the the occurrence of anomalies like the cracks, porosity inside manufactured parts and so on present a disadvantage to be unsuitable and unacceptable. Many researchers attempt to reduce some defects CMTed aluminium parts. [4] Have varied the speed of the wire feeding and travel in order to analyze the effect of heat input on the properties of Al5356 block. With the same issues (heat input) for the deposition of Al-5356 [5]) The lowest heat input used was able to refine the grain structure and reduce the porosity slightly. Hauser, T et al. [6] have studied the porosity inside aluminum alloys parts, based on this investigation; they have observed that the high gas flow rate is, the high porosity is. This outcome due to the rapid solidification of aluminum in the melt pool by forced convection. Filling strategies in order to reducing porosity in Al-Mg WAAM parts and their impact on

mechanical properties have been examined by M. Arana et al [7]; it was shown that the type of deposition strategy is directly affecting the porosity observed in parts fabricated by the CMT technique. The effect of filler metal feed speed (VAF) on cracking in CMT welding for Al-Si alloys was discussed by L. Huang et al[8], who concluded that increasing VAF increases the susceptibility to solidification cracking, in addition to the state of strength, the melt is also modified, causing crack propagation. In 2023 Wieczorowski, M et al. [9] have investigated on the characterization of 5356 Aluminum Walls manufactured by WAAM. The results allowed them to conclude that pores diameter are slightly decrease in the function of the increment of travel speed and cooling time. The present work is focused on find out and prove of drawbacks of using high currents when 3D printing parts of Al-5356 Alloy using the CMT technique from morphological, mechanical and tribological properties point of view.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

The filler metal used is a wire of 5356 aluminum alloy with 1 mm of diameter. The latter alloy provides a good weldability and high corrosion resistance for containing Mg elements [3]. The

elemental composition of 5356 aluminum given in Table 1[10].

Table 1. Chemical compositions of Al-5356

Element	Al %	Cr%	Cu%	Fe%
Min	92,9	0,05	-	-
Max	95,3	0,2	0,1	0,4
Element	Mg%	Mn%	Si%	Ti%
Min	4,5	0,05	-	0,06
Max	5,5	0,2	0,25	0,2

Quantitative analysis of the EDS spectrum (see figure 1) showed that the parts was primarily Al-Mg alloy with the following proportions Al: 89.81%, Mg: 5.25%. Besides the Mg element, the oxygen peak is observed due to the Aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃) layer formed on the surface [11, 12] from the surrounding oxidizing environment and the oxidation of the surface.

Fig. 1 EDS analysis data for Al-5356 CMTed parts

A WAAM-CMT system, composed of a Fronius TPS 500i welding machine, connected to a shielding gas system of argon (99.99%) and computer numerical control (CNC), as a positioning system is used to perform the experiments (see Fig.2):

Fig. 2 CMT Power source and CNC table

2.2 Experimental procedures

Two types of samples produced using the CMT technique (walls (10x5 cm) and massive parts with two types of filling strategy (zigzag and grid)) (see Figure 3). The stick-out was kept at 15 mm. the table 2 containing the process parameters throughout parts manufacture:

Table 2. Process parameters for WAAM-CMT of Al-5356

Parameters	Values	Parameters	Values
Welding mode	MIG CMT	Gas flow (Argon)	10 l/min
Operating mode	4 time	Current	Variable (A)
Material	Al 5356	Traval speed	2400mm/min
Diameter	1 mm	Torch increment	0.50 mm
Synchropulse frequency	0.5 Hz	Wire feed speed	6.4m/min

Fig. 3 Walls and massive parts side view

In the process of (CMT), the current plays an essential role in controlling the transfer of metal between the aluminium wire and the workpiece. In this process, the filler metal is conveyed into the melt pool with a pulsed movement (pushing and pulling) [13, 14]. The phase when the the pushing movement happen, the arc is extinguished (pulling movement) and the current is reduced to a low level[15]. A high current intensity needs more time to reduce to the low level compared to low currents wich can cause very rapid solidification. The rapid solidification of aluminium is a drawback for CMTed parts and that what we will see in the next chapter.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cross-section of aluminium walls and massive parts manufactured at process parameters mentioned in the table 2 are shown in Figure 4:

Fig. 4: Cross-sections of the walls (a) and massive parts(b)

3.1 Massive parts result discussion

The figure 5 depicts the effect of filling strategies on the parts form, it can be seen that the full filling was reached at 40A with grid strategy. Whereas, the full filling does not be reached even 70A with Zigzag strategy.

Fig. 5 Interior view of the produced massive parts

At the first sight, it seems that a good current for printing with zigzag parts is 70A, but the microhardness gave other results. The table 2 lists the microhardness measurements (Hv). The latter is carried out using a Vickers hardness tester (Durometer Qness M30) by applying a load of 2.5 N for 15s as a waiting time at charging point. The charge speed is 0,5 mm/min

Table 3. Micro-hardness measurements of massive parts

40A (grid)	79	88	88	88
60A (zigzag)	85	76	76	81
70A (zigzag)	81	77	79	77

As we can see from the measurements in the table 3, the strategy grid has a uniform hardness of 88 Hv. The statistics of zigzag filling strategy, at I=60A give an average of $Hv=79.50$ with a standard deviation of $\sigma=4.36$, which means that the hardness values are dispersed in relation to the average, whereas at I=70A the average is $Hv=78.50$ with $\sigma=1.91$. It can be seen that the hardness of parts at I=70A tends towards homogeneity, but a lower hardness than at 60A, due to the rapid solidification of the material. From this outcome we can obviously confirm that the high current is, the low hardness is. Besides of this results, the analyzing of the pore formation in CMTed parts, we can see from the figure 6 which presents the porosity inside aluminum massive parts at 60 and 70A, the high current is the high size of pores is.

Fig. 6: porosity inside massive parts

This result is, undoubtedly, due to rapid solidification of aluminium, caused by high current intensity which not leave enough time to escape the gas from the melt pool.

3.2 Walls result discussion

The microstructure of the walls in different current intensities was analysed with the metallographic. The figure 7 represents the microstructure of the 5356-aluminum walls.

Fig. 7: microstructure of walls at different current (I=50,70 and 90A)

From this figure it can be seen that the micrograph of specimens shows a random granular structure with fine grain boundaries with a different grain size that are equiaxed grains. Comparing the microstructure of three figures (7-a, 7-b and 7-c), it can be seen that the lower the intensity is, the smaller the grain size is. In addition, the pore size is larger at higher current intensities, which is due to the rapid solidification of aluminum.

Fig.8 SEM images of the printed walls at (50,70 and 90A)

The figure 8 depicts the SEM images of the printed walls at different current intensities. It can be observed that there are no obvious shrinkages in the CMTed walls, but a number of pores exists inside the walls and this phenomenon is inherent to CMTed aluminium parts as shown in Figure 8(a). those pores are filled with hydrogen due to the different solubility between hydrogen in the solid and liquid states of Al-5356 that cannot escape from the melt pool[16,17].

On the other hand, shrinkages and porosity are highly visible and even more important when the current increases (see Figure 8(b) and Figure 8(c)).

Hardness measurements of CMTed parts is carried out using a Vickers hardness tester and mentioned in the table 4. The measurement are taken from the top of walls to the bottom(see figure 9-a)

Table 4: Hardness measurements of walls

I (A)	I	II	III	IV	V	Mean	σ
50	68.1	67.4	73.2	73.8	72	70,90	2.96
70	68.0	68.4	71.8	71.2	71.4	70,16	1.80
90	63.4	69.7	66.5	71.3	69.6	68,10	3.15

Fig. 9. Hardness tests a) positions inside specimen b) variation as a function of the position inside walls

The figure 9-d depicts the variation of hardness as a function of the position inside walls divided into equal intervals of points. It can be remarked that the high hardness corresponds to a low current (black one). Whereas, the high current has a low hardness and dispersed values (green one) due to the internal defects as discussed before that confirm the drawbacks of high current.

A tribological study, of CMTed Aluminium walls, has been done with an applied force of 30N for 15 min and a frequency of 10Hz. The figure 10 shows friction coefficient static and dynamic at different current intensities.

a)I=50

Fig. 10 Schematic of a typical friction coefficient

It can be seen that there is no significant difference in the coefficient of friction. However, a lower value either friction coefficient static or dynamic corresponds to the high current (COF stat = 0.52 and COF dyn = 0.4642). Wear resistance test carried out with Rtec instruments MTF5000 and mass losses calculations during before and after operation of the frequency paver on the surface of wall cross-sections exhibit a lower specific wear rate at I = 90A (0.4 mg), whereas, about 0.2mg of mass loss for 50 and 70A. Note that the force applied to the specimens is 30N for 15 min at a frequency of 10Hz.

4 CONCLUSION

Summing up the results of the impact of the current intensities on CMTed aluminium parts from morphological, mechanical and tribological properties point of view in order to find out the drawbacks of using high currents when 3D printing, it is possible to conclude that

- The full filling for massive parts reached at low intensity (40A) with grid filling strategy.

- A good current for printing with zigzag parts is 70A, However, the low intensity presents a high hardness.
- The high current causes a very rapid solidification of the aluminum.
- The high current is the high size of pores.
- The micrograph of specimens shows a random granular structure with fine grain boundaries with a different grain size that are equiaxed grains.
- The lower the current intensity is, the smaller the grain size is. In addition, the pore size is larger at higher current intensities.
- From SEM images of printed walls at different current intensities, shrinkages and porosity are highly visible and even more important when the current increases.
- The high hardness corresponds to a low current. Whereas, the high current has a low hardness and dispersed values due to the internal defects as discussed before that confirm the drawbacks of high current.
- A tribological study, of CMTed Aluminium walls shows that the lower value either friction coefficient static or dynamic corresponds to the high current and the high current intensity is, the lower specific wear rate is.

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